

The TransContinuum Initiative: eliminating the silos in order to achieve a better orchestration of complex applications

The continuum of computing

By MARC DURANTON, MICHAEL MALMS and MARCIN OSTASZ

As explained in the 2017 HiPEAC Vision [1], ICT is expanding from cyberspace and it is now interacting with us directly, e.g. in self-driving cars, driverless underground and overground trains, factories and cities. In this new paradigm, applications are not built around a single piece of code running on a single machine, but span across various computing resources distributed in multiple locations. The notion of a continuum of computing has emerged, which denotes a set of computing resources and software (the smartphone, the communication infrastructure, the cloud) acting together in order to complete a complex task involving multiple systems and multiple technologies. This concept has been proposed by HiPEAC and promoted in its Vision roadmaps for the last five years. This has led to the creation of the “TransContinuum Initiative”, which involves various European organisations including ETP4HPC, ECSO, BDVA, 5GIA, EU MATHS IN, CLAIRE, AIOTI and HiPEAC with the objective to promote these concepts further through concrete actions.

Key insights

- Distributed systems are required to operate applications on various computing resources distributed in different locations.
- Distributed systems need to be developed in such a way that they ensure performance, efficiency, security, reliability and trust.
- The task calls for a number of communities to work together to achieve the orchestration of this complex set of various systems and software (which now is mainly achieved by ad-hoc approaches) and to develop interoperability, both in the protocol between systems and in the data structures.
- The cross-disciplinary “TransContinuum Initiative” (TCI) constitutes an attempt to “break the silos” and achieve better efficiency through horizontal collaborations among various organisations.

Key recommendations

- Cross-disciplinary work to achieve better efficiency through horizontal collaborations among various organisations is required to achieve the success of tomorrow’s solutions that will form a “continuum” of computing.
- Software is becoming increasingly distributed across platforms and devices and therefore programming has to be reinvented with languages and tools to orchestrate collaborative distributed and decentralized components, as well as components augmented with interface contracts covering both functional and non-functional properties.
- Interoperability is mandatory, not only in the format of data that need to be recognized by all elements of the continuum, but also interfaces, protocols and API.
- All solutions should support increased software and hardware sustainability, and a high-level of cybersecurity to rely on dependable and resilient components, services and digital infrastructures.
- Algorithmic efficiency will need to be drastically improved (e.g. more efficient AI), which requires development of basic modelling, simulation and optimization methodologies in data-rich environments (MSODE), including model-order reduction. Management and deployment of large-scale application workflows will have to be adapted or invented.
- Building over existing technologies will facilitate acceptance, ease the development and reduce the cost, even if new software layers need to be added on top of existing solutions.

Continuum of computing explained

Despite the fact that there are still a lot of standalone applications, applications in general rely increasingly on other applications to improve their efficiency, while some of them are not even able to work in standalone mode.

For example, the “cyberspace” of aircraft is composed of a multiplicity of tasks, from collecting data from sensors, to controlling the engines and ensuring the safety of those on board, and these tasks are done by a multiplicity of computing resources, from the small micro-controller integrated in a sensor to the main on-board computers (OBC). However, planes are also connected with other planes and with the ground, not only for air-traffic control, but also to (indirectly) obtain the results of the supercomputers that are involved in predicting the weather. They are part of a complex orchestration not only of other aircraft, but also of computing hardware and software. The trajectory of the aircraft is predicted even before it takes off in order to ensure that it will be alone in its space and will have a slot for landing.

In the factories of today, machines do not work independently but are connected and orchestrated. Sensors are everywhere

(IoT), collecting data from each machine and how they perform their processes. All this data is processed increasingly locally in order to provide meaningful information on how the machine works. All this information is collected and processed increasingly on the fly to maximize efficiency for the entire factory. In parallel, analysis of the data allows predictive maintenance to be performed. In more advanced systems, a complete model of the factory, its digital twin, running on high performance computers and fed by the actual data, allows further enhancement of the global efficiency, and advance prediction of what should be done to control the various actuators in the factory. Techniques using artificial intelligence can also be used alongside numerical simulation to enhance the parts where explicit modelling is not easy. This forms a kind of complete “continuum” that spans from data sources to commands (controlling physical devices) which is depicted in Figure 1.

Even for consumers, **photography** and **sharing photos** through social networks also involve a multiplicity of ICT devices working together: the picture is first pre-processed by a digital signal processor, then is upgraded using AI accelerators to improve it before being stored in the

memory of the smartphone. It can also be postprocessed in order to be efficiently sent with its associated metadata, which could include the localization provided by GPS. GPS information is also generated by a set of computing tasks, some of them being done in a satellite in order to send the right signal to the GPS receiver and its associated software in the smartphone. Then the picture, with its corresponding metadata, is sent to baseband stations – also computers- and through several steps enters a data centre (cloud) and then gets distributed over several processors or even data centres to make it appear on a social media feed.

The examples above illustrate the emergence of the **continuum of computing**, i.e. a set of computing resources and software (the smartphone, the communication infrastructure, the cloud) acting together in order to achieve a complex task of e.g. making the picture you took accessible to your friends.

Even if the cloud is mainly driven by non-European organizations, Europe has the potential to be present in the “edge” and “deep edge” solutions if it doesn’t wait too long. As explained in the HiPEAC Vision 2019 [2], there is an alternance of centralized then decentralized tendencies in computing: from 1970s computing centres, to distributed set of PCs, to the cloud where most of processing is done. Nowadays, the pendulum is swinging more towards having “intelligence at the edge” rather than just having all computing done in the cloud. But the window of opportunity for Europe will be small: edge systems are very diverse, and being able to deliver a high diversity of systems, customized to particular applications, quickly put on the market with a high productivity (and therefore low cost) will be key for success. Furthermore, AI could help to improve this productivity. For example, in the factory and plane examples, a lot of processing has to be done locally, for safety, latency or privacy reasons, and cannot rely on communicating all the raw data to “the cloud”.

The TransContinuum

The term TransContinuum describes the defining characteristic of the infrastructure

Figure 1: A typical mixed simulation: IoT and edge, machine learning workflow [3]. This is a generic high-level model, i.e. all elements depicted or a subset thereof are present in every complex system.

Figure 2: A pictorial view of the Continuum of Computing (see the chapter for more explanations).

required for the convergence of data and compute capabilities in many leading edge industrial and scientific use scenarios. A paradigm change is needed: we will have to design systems encompassing millions of compute devices distributed over scientific instruments, IoT, supercomputers and cloud systems through LAN, WLAN and 5G networks.

In this continuum, edge, fog and cloud computing platforms are being pulled close together into what will likely become a seamless execution environment, as depicted at the bottom part of Figure 2. This change is being driven by a massively increasing amount of value-added applications targeting mobile, handheld, wearable and unattended devices.

We are observing a continuous miniaturization of computing and storage devices, as well as their ubiquitous deployment ranging from data centres to the edge and beyond. There is also the need to enable workflows beyond single control domains like a data centre. Therefore, a new overall system architecture must be designed to accommodate the ecosystem changes (environmental and technological) to be expected in the coming decades and to integrate horizontally the different actors.

The challenges associated with the “continuum of computing”

Software is becoming increasingly distributed, becoming a “continuum of

computing” across platforms and devices, from the “deep edge” to the cloud, HPC and data centres. Programming has to be reinvented for this, with languages and tools to orchestrate collaborative distributed and decentralized components, as well as components augmented with interface contracts covering both functional and non-functional properties. Data collected by deep-edge devices is concentrated and processed by edge computing, consolidated by federations of systems (fog computing) or, if required, travels to the cloud or to HPC centres to feed simulations that facilitate decisions on actions to be taken, e.g. for managing fleets of vehicles, complex factories or air traffic, therefore closing the loop.

The new demands and challenges, having an impact on the need to combine data, storage and compute, to have them distributed across the continuum, and ensure lifecycle maintenance and resource efficiencies, are pushing for drastically increased software and hardware sustainability. Furthermore, the need to provide high-level cybersecurity to rely on dependable and resilient components, services and digital infrastructures is changing the game profoundly. Efficiency and resilience will have to reach levels never achieved thus far, while taking into account the intrinsic distributed and heterogeneous nature of the **continuum**. In addition, the question of dealing with very high volumes of data needs to be addressed, and the preponderance of quality versus quantity will become

unavoidable. These considerations will be relevant to all components.

Interoperability is mandatory, not only in the format of data that need to be recognized by all elements of the continuum, but also interfaces, protocols and APIs. Today, there is one system that connects billions of heterogeneous devices, from the smallest IoT device to the largest data centre: the internet. We propose therefore that the TransContinuum runs mainly on top of existing technologies, such as those used in the internet, like TCP/IP, RESTful services, etc. Building over existing technologies will also facilitate acceptance, even if new software layers might need to be added on top.

Long-lifetime hardware devices will have to be reconfigurable, modular, exchangeable and self-aware in order to be operational over extended periods. Algorithmic efficiency will need to be drastically improved (e.g. more efficient AI), which requires development of basic modelling, simulation and optimization methodologies in data-rich environments (MSODE), including model-order reduction. Management and deployment of large-scale application workflows will have to be adapted or invented. Network protocols will have to offer better control over the data logistics.

Furthermore, it is widely recognized that AI will play a central role in these extreme-scale, continuum infrastructures. This will occur at three levels:

- “AI for digital infrastructure” addresses how AI-inspired techniques can pilot and monitor the continuum and, in so doing, provide solutions to the points listed above.
- “Digital infrastructure for AI” tackles the question of re-designing the e-infrastructure to efficiently deal with data analysis and machine learning, which means, amongst other things, tuning of data access, I/O, low precision arithmetic, and moving code and data to where they will be most efficiently performed.
- “AI for science, industry and societal challenges” deals with the ever-increasing need to exploit AI techniques for extreme-scale, combining data and compute through the interpretation and coupling of computing results, measure-

ments and observations (e.g. digital twins in extreme earth modelling, combining climate models with satellite data and on-ground sensors).

The overall objective is to target high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) solutions (7 and more), based on horizontal synergies and interdependencies between all the concerned digital infrastructure technologies: HPC, big data, machine learning, IoT, 5G, cybersecurity, processor technology (EPI) and robotics. All of these components of the digital infrastructure will, together, be able to address critical societal challenges and sustainable development goals by mobilizing their amazing potential all the way across the continuum.

The TransContinuum Initiative (TCI)

The TransContinuum Initiative was launched in the wake of ETP4HPC’s collaborative work with five other associations and projects to prepare the latest edition of the ETP4HPC Strategic Research Agenda for HPC in Europe [5], which was published in March 2020. Currently, it involves ETP4HPC, ECSO, BDVA, 5GIA, EU MATHS IN, CLAIRE, AIOTI and HiPEAC.

The TransContinuum Initiative will focus on the following five objectives:

- Identify priorities and recommendation for European R&I work programs: jointly we will elaborate recommendations for R&D to be carried out in EU-funded

work programs addressing challenges in the digital continuum. The recommendations will cover challenges in technological (hardware and software) functionality, interoperability, and APIs. New standards, best practices, methodologies and project-type related suggestions will also be generated. Applications deployed in the digital continuum are addressed wherever needed.

- Engage in discussions with European R&I funding agencies and R&D programs (e.g. JUs, Missions): the recommendations will be presented to EU-funding entities such as Joint Undertakings (JUs) and applicable programs within the MFF 2021-2027. TCI representatives will be available to present and explain these recommendations as well to discuss any possible further analysis and elaborations.
- Generate and foster an interdisciplinary network of experts: we look forward to a lively exchange of ideas about EC work programs, calls and related events, events of partner organizations and potentially joint activities. We will jointly analyze new industrial and scientific use cases to better understand the challenges presented, together with an identification of “weak signals” for preparing for the future. This is a pre-requisite for any R&I recommendations and it also facilitates the forming of interdisciplinary consortia for the upcoming calls.
- Contribute to SR(I)As and other partners’ documents: based on the results of the joint work mentioned above, contributions to the Strategic Research (and

Innovation) Agendas or any other road-mapping documents issued by participating partners will be offered.

- Contribute to the 5 Horizon Europe missions: one of the first pragmatic actions will be to design the contribution of the concept of digital twin to the Horizon Europe missions (adaptation to climate change including societal transformation, cancer, healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters, climate-neutral and smart cities, soil health and food). To achieve their respective goals, these missions will require digital technologies, in which digital twins should constitute the critical component.

References

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Marc Duranton is the coordinator of the HiPEAC Vision 2021 document, and also participant of ETP4HPC and involved in its SRA.

Michael Malms is the SRA lead editor within the office team of ETP4HPC and main initiator and coordinator of the TransContinuum Initiative.

Marcin Ostasz is an ETP4HPC Office Expert who co-manages the delivery of ETP4HPC’s roadmapping documents and other related tasks.

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Figure 3: A pictorial view of the Transcontinuum.